

Thin Layer Chromatography of Metal Ions Complexed with Anils. Part V

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Manuscript received 17 February 1977, revised 13 March 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

p-Diethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal forms coloured complexes with several transition and nontransition metal ions. Several complex mixtures have been resolved by Thin layer chromatography. Chromatogram fragments were scrapped and eluted; concentration of elutes were deduced spectrophotometrically.

IN continuation of studies on ketoanils as analytical reagents¹⁻⁶ in the detection, separation and determination of metal ions it has been found that *p*-diethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal⁷ forms coloured complexes with transition as well as nontransition elements. The colours of the complexes are fairly stable.

Present paper reports the thin layer chromatographic (TLC) detection and separation of Pt(IV), Au(III), Hg(II), UO₂(II), Be(II), Mg(II), Sb(III), Bi(III) metal ions complexed with *p*-diethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal on silica gel layers. Chromatogram fragments were scrapped and eluted; concentration of elutes were determined spectrophotometrically. In order to know the extent to which this method is applicable limits of maximum separation of the metal ions in their mixtures have been shown.

Empirical molecular formulae and electrolytic nature of the complexes were deduced by their analyses and molar conductance results. Reagents having carbonyl and azomethine coordinating groups act as bidentate ligand to form chelates with metal ions.

Experimental

Preparation of Solutions :

Ligand and complexes of metal chloride were prepared by dissolving their known quantities in alcohol. Metal chloride (B. D. H. or J. M. Products) solutions were standardised⁸ before use while ligand or complex solutions were used directly.

Isolation and Analysis of Complexes

Equimolar solutions of the reactants were mixed in stoichiometric ratio (ligand slight excess); reaction mixtures were concentrated on water bath and products were crystallised out. Complexes were repeatedly washed with ether to remove unreacted ligand if any, recrystallized from acetone and dried on anhydrous calcium chloride under reduced pressure. Platinum complex which separates from the reaction mixture was washed with ether and dried. All the complexes were analysed for nitrogen, chlorine and metal contents at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and results are given in Table-1.

Physical Measurements

Conductometric measurements on the complex solutions were made with Toshniwal's conductivity bridge by dip-cell method. Absorbance measurements were made with Bausch & Lomb 'Spectronic-20' spectrophotometer.

Preparation and Development of TLC Plates

Glass plates (18×3cm and 18×10cm) were coated with silica gel freed from iron and chloride ions and mixed with starch (E. Merck) as binder (24 : 1, w/w) to prepare layers 0.1 cm thickness by self designed apparatus⁹. The coated plates were dried at ~100° for 2-3 hr. in an oven. For qualitative analysis sample solutions were applied with fine capillaries while for quantitative analysis they were applied with micro pipet on 18×10cm glass plates. The R_F values were determined on 18×3cm glass strips and results were checked using 18×10cm glass plates.

Dry loaded plates were developed in glass chambers with ground-in-lids by ascending technique. The time

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TABLE 1—EMPIRICAL MOLECULAR FORMULA AND ELECTROLYTIC NATURE OF COMPLEXES

Compound	Elemental analysis						Molar conductance
	Nitrogen (%)		Chlorine (%)		Metal (%)		
	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	
[PtL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5.57	5.58	14.12	13.94	19.40	19.18	81.5 (1:2) (Polar)
[AuLCl.H ₂ O]Cl ₂	4.66	4.90	17.70	18.0	32.75	32.34	153.0 (1:2) „
[HgLCl.H ₂ O]Cl.5H ₂ O	4.09	3.96	10.76	10.50	30.41	30.20	37.4 (1 1) „
[UO ₂ L ₂]Cl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5.55	5.40	7.03	6.82	23.59	23.36	104.5 (1:2) „
[BeLCl.H ₂ O]Cl.3H ₂ O	6.48	6.60	16.43	16.14	2.08	2.00	68.25 (1:1) „
[MgL ₂ Cl ₂]6H ₂ O	7.51	7.23	9.52	9.31	3.26	3.18	21.22 (Non polar)
[Sb ₂ LCl ₅ .5H ₂ O]Cl.6H ₂ O	3.00	2.89	22.79	22.95	26.04	26.34	49.00 (1:1) (Polar)
[Bi ₂ LCl ₂ .8H ₂ O]Cl ₄ .4H ₂ O	2.48	2.49	18.90	18.72	37.09	37.30	327.4 (1:4) „

TABLE 2—SPOT COLOUR, λ_{max} AND R_F OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Spot colour	λ _{max}	BuOH AcOH BuOH- BuOH- BuOH- MeCN Me ₂ CO Me ₂ CO- Aq. Aq. Aq.						-CHCl ₃	BuOH	BuOH- AcOH (2:1)	BuOH- AcOH (1:2)	
			(2:1)	(1:1)	(1:2)	(2:1)	(2:1)	(2:1)					(2:1)
Ligand (L)	Green	330	—	—	—	—	—	0.41	0.93	—	—	—	0.65
[PtL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ .6H ₂ O	Light pink	360	.99	.96	.05	.74	.02	.90	0.35	.08	.00	.10	0.13
[AuLCl.H ₂ O]Cl ₂	Light Brown	360	.99	.99	.98	.74	.97	.99	0.45	.11	.00	.00	0.00
[HgLCl.H ₂ O]Cl.5H ₂ O	Pink	420	.99	.99	.07	.76	.02	.59	0.95	.12	.00	.06	.08
[UO ₂ L ₂]Cl ₂ .6H ₂ O	Pink	360	.99	.00	.08	.76	.99	.97	.88	.17	.00	.00	0.00
[BeLCl.H ₂ O]Cl.3H ₂ O	Light Brown	520	.99	.56	.06	.00	.03	.00	.21	.20	.00	.00	0.00
[MgL ₂ Cl ₂].6H ₂ O	Brown	420	.99	.56	.07	.00	.01	.63	0.97	.91	.00	.24	.00
[Sb ₂ LCl ₅ .5H ₂ O]Cl.6H ₂ O	Light yellow	520	.99	.97	.99	.78	.97	.63	0.35	.18	.00	.00	.00
[Bi ₂ LCl ₂ .8H ₂ O]Cl ₄ .4H ₂ O	Light Pink	520	.99	.98	.96	.72	.98	.00	0.25	.11	.00	.06	.00
Developing time (min.)			50	45	35	38	30	10	7	18	60	68	52
Room temperature = 37°C													

of development given in Table-2 is for a distance of 8-10 cm travelled by the solvent front. The developed plates were air dried and the spots were clearly visible in day light.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry of the complexes in their solutions were found out spectrophotometrically following Mole-Ratio method¹⁰. Analysis results establishing similar stoichiometric ratios in solid complexes have been used

to deduce their empirical molecular formulae as noted in Table-1. Electrolytic nature of the products determined conductometrically on alcoholic solutions with molar conductance values have been given in the same table.

The R_F values of the individual complexes were determined by migrating pure complexes. R_F values given in Table-2 are those obtained by migrating pure complexes.

A perusal of TLC data clearly explores that best separation of following mixtures of metal ions in their complex form can be achieved only in acetone in which mixtures of maximum four complexes are resolvable and spots are well separated. Although a quaternary mixture of Be(II) or Bi(III); Hg(II) or Sb(III) or Mg(II), Pt(IV), Au(III) or UO₂(II) ions may also be resolved in methylcyanide.

S. NO.	Mixture	Solvent	
1.	Mg(II) + UO ₂ (II) + Au(III) + Bi(III) (0.97) (0.88) (0.45) (0.25)	Acetone	Mixture 1 : Mg, 2ppm ; UO ₂ , 11ppm ; Au, 8ppm ; Bi, 7ppm Mixture 2 : Mg, 4ppm ; UO ₂ , 30ppm ; Pt, 26.5ppm ; Bi, 16ppm
2.	Mg(II) + UO ₂ (II) + Pt(IV) + Bi(III) (0.97) (0.88) (0.35) (0.25)	Acetone	Mixture 3 : Hg, 4.5ppm ; Sb, 49.5ppm ; Be; 9.5ppm.
3.	Hg(II) + Sb(III) + Be(II) (0.95) (0.35) (0.21)	Acetone	

The effects of layer thickness and size of plate on R_F were also studied and it was found that only layer thickness had the significant influence on the R_F.

Quantitative Estimations

For the quantitative analysis mixtures having different concentrations of their components were applied to the plates and developed in acetone. Chromatogram fragments were scrapped and complexes were eluted from the adsorbent with alcohol and each elute

was made upto 5 ml. Optical density of the elutes were determined spectrophotometrically at the λ_{max} of corresponding components and concentrations in ppm were deduced from respective calibration curves prepared under similar conditions (Fig. 1). Maximum quantities of the complexes which could be resolved by the present method are :

It was found that optical density of ligand solutions was fairly considerable at the λ_{max} of the respective complexes and it varied linearly with the concentration. This infers that presence of ligand will interfere the determination of metal ions as their complexes.

Acknowledgement

One of us (A.P.T.) owe his indebtedness to Shri Raghu Nandan Sharma, Principal, D.A.V. College, Bulandshahr for the encouragement to undertake this work. We are also thankful to Dr. P. C. Gupta, Principal, N.R.E C. College, Khurja for providing the facilities.

Fig. 1

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